

Microcirculation and cardiovascular risk: Diagnostic value and clinical relevance

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Abstract

Arterial hypertension (AH) is one of the most common diseases in modern medicine, affecting a significant portion of the adult population. Microcirculatory endothelial dysfunction plays a central role in the pathogenesis and progression of the disease, contributing to the development of organ complications. Within this context, microcirculation has emerged as a key target area of study in AH and cardiovascular risk (CVR).

Low-grade vascular inflammatory processes and oxidative stress are major mediators in the development and complications of AH. Increasing scientific evidence points to a complex interplay between genetic and environmental factors that determine the individual risk of developing AH. Microcirculation represents the intersection of these pathogenetic mechanisms and is subject to morphological and functional alterations determined by the prolonged effects of high arterial pressure.

The aim of this review is to analyze the microcirculatory changes associated with the pathogenesis of AH and their diagnostic and prognostic value in modern medicine. In conclusion, the study of microcirculation has been established as a reliable, noninvasive method of assessment of the microcirculatory disturbances occurring in the course of AH and may contribute to more accurate diagnosis and monitoring of the disease, as well as to the identification of metabolic disturbances associated with increased cardiovascular risk.

Keywords

microcirculation, arterial hypertension, capillaroscopy

Introduction

Arterial hypertension (AH) is one of the most common diseases in modern medicine, affecting a significant portion of the adult population. A key aspect in the progression of the disease and its complications is microcirculatory endothelial dysfunction. In the 50 references we used, 17 of which were from the last 5 years, we aimed to investigate the microcirculatory changes associated with the pathogenesis of AH and their diagnostic value in arterial hypertension and related metabolic disorders in modern medicine.

Role of the endothelial dysfunction for the microcirculation in arterial hypertension

The endothelium is an endocrine-active tissue that regulates vascular tone through the secretion of vasoactive substances capable of inducing relaxation or contraction of the underlying vascular smooth muscle. The best characterized endothelium-dependent relaxing factor (EDRF) is nitric oxide (NO), which activates soluble guanylate cyclase in the smooth muscle cells of the vascular wall. This leads to an increased production of cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP), which initiates vasodilation (Fig. 1).

Furthermore, endothelial cells can induce hyperpolarization of the vascular smooth muscle cell membrane (endothelium-dependent hyperpolarization, EDH), with hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) playing a key role in this process (Vanhoutte et al. 2017).

In addition to the vasodilating factors, the endothelium secretes vasoconstrictor molecules, including endothelins, prostaglandin H_2 , thromboxane A_2 , sodium cations, angiotensin II, and endothelial constrictor factor. Endothelial dysfunction represents an imbalance between

the vasodilator and vasoconstrictor factors and is a major pathophysiological mechanism in the development of arterial hypertension and the associated vascular damage.

Oxidative stress is a common mechanism of cellular and tissue damage in various organs and systems involved in the pathogenesis of arterial hypertension and the associated target organ damage. Data from experimental models and cultured cells confirm a direct link between the reactive oxygen species (ROS) – superoxide, hydrogen peroxide, peroxynitrite, redox signaling – and hypertension. Of particular importance in this process are NADPH oxidase, endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS), mitochondrial-generated ROS, and endoplasmic reticulum stress (ER stress), which contribute to the redox imbalance in hypertension (Griendling et al. 2021).

Inflammation and oxidative stress as factors for microcirculatory changes

Low-grade inflammation and associated oxidative stress play a key role in the pathogenesis of arterial hypertension (AH) and the organ damage induced by it. Activation of the innate immune response mediated by neutrophils, dendritic cells, monocytes/macrophages, and unconventional $\gamma\delta$ T lymphocytes leads to vascular inflammation. Evidence from contemporary studies suggests that the adaptive immune response also contributes to the development of AH as well as vascular and renal damage. In particular, effector T-lymphocytes (Th1, Th2, and Th17) play an important role in microvascular remodeling, as cytokines produced by these cells induce increased oxidative stress and endothelial dysfunction and contribute to the target organ damage in AH. Furthermore, there are suggestions for the involvement of specific immune cell subpopulations in the processes of development and regression of microvascular remodeling in hypertensive disease (Rizzoni et al. 2022).

Figure 1. Biological importance of eNOS (Bivolarska 2024).

Microcirculatory changes in hypertension

Arterial hypertension significantly affects microcirculation, causing structural and functional changes that contribute to systemic and organ-specific vascular damage. Microcirculation includes arterioles, capillaries, and venules less than 20 μm in diameter, which play key roles in oxygenation, nutrient metabolism, and maintenance of tissue homeostasis. In the context of hypertension, microvascular remodeling and capillary rarefaction lead to reduced vascular density and elasticity, which increases the vascular resistance and contributes to organ damage.

The main pathophysiological mechanisms of microvascular dysfunction in AH include endothelial dysfunction – impaired production of vasodilatory factors; oxidative stress – increased reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation; excessive collagen accumulation – structural changes leading to vascular stiffening and fibrosis.

These pathological processes impair the bioavailability of nitric oxide (NO), increase ROS production, and induce inflammation that progressively leads to vascular dysfunction and damage to end organs such as the heart, kidneys, brain, and retina (Durante et al. 2024).

Genetic and epigenetic factors influencing microcirculation

Current understanding of genome-environment interactions is revealing new mechanisms by which genetic and epigenetic factors contribute to the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disease. A growing body of evidence suggests that epigenetic regulation, along with genetic determinants, plays a central role in the control of blood pressure and that there is a complex interplay between heritable and environmental factors that influences the individual risk of arterial hypertension (AH) (Nikolova and Popov 2008; Griendling et al. 2021).

It has recently been found that epigenetic changes, including DNA methylation, posttranslational histone modifications, ATP-dependent chromatin remodeling, and noncoding RNA transcripts, play an increasing role in the development of cardiovascular disease. Although epigenetic modifications were long thought to be established during embryonic development and remain stable, increasing evidence suggests that these processes can be dynamic and modified in response to environmental factors (Nikolova 2009; Kietzmann et al. 2017).

Microcirculation as a target area in arterial hypertension

Microcirculation is emerging as a key target area in the study of AH and the associated cardiovascular risk (CVR).

One of the main factors determining the effectiveness of microcirculation is the balance between the number of functioning capillaries and the volume of circulating blood (Güven et al. 2020; Laurent et al. 2022). The optimal tissue oxygen supply and energy balance depend on the efficient redistribution of blood flow, whereby active structures receive an advantage in blood supply at the expense of less active areas (Güven et al. 2020). Blood flow redistribution is regulated by changes in arteriolar smooth muscle tone, resulting in variations in the capillary hemodynamic pressure. Disturbances in the vasomotor activity, commonly seen in microcirculatory dysfunction, lead to stasis of blood in tissues and shunting of the capillary blood flow. As a result, capillaries become passive conductors of blood, contributing to local hypoxia and tissue damage.

A key parameter of capillary blood flow is its velocity, which is an indicator of the efficiency of microcirculatory regulation (Junga and Ramplingb 2016; White et al. 2018).

Digital capillaroscopy – a method of studying microcirculation

Digital nail bed capillaroscopy is an established non-invasive method for direct visualization and analysis of small blood vessels using a digital microscope. Wide-angle capillaroscopy (widefield capillaroscopy) allows assessment of capillary density, morphology, and dimensions of individual capillaries in the arterial, venous, and transitional areas. In addition, the method provides information on the condition of surrounding tissues and structural changes in microcirculation.

Digital capillaroscopy allows analysis of intracapillary hemodynamics, including blood flow velocity and rheological properties of blood. The main advantages of the method are its non-invasiveness, high informativeness, and the possibility of “*in vivo*” study of the qualitative and quantitative parameters of capillary circulation (Rizzoni et al. 2011).

Capillary density and hemodynamic characteristics

Capillary blood flow studies are most commonly performed on the nail bed of the fingers of the left hand, with capillary density varying depending on the anatomic localization. In the nail bed, the number of functioning capillaries is usually 50–60 capillaries/ mm^2 , with the highest capillary density reported in the fourth finger (Baboshina 2018; Mishra et al. 2021).

In addition to the capillary density, the perivascular area and hemodynamic parameters of the blood flow are of key importance. Under normal conditions, periodic fluctuations in blood flow velocity are observed, related to the autonomic regulation of microcirculation (Mishra et al. 2021; Ben-Ami et al. 2022).

Relationship between capillary rarefaction and arterial hypertension

Reduced capillary density leads to structural and functional changes in microcirculation that contribute to increased vascular resistance and elevated arterial pressure (Duranteau et al. 2023). These changes have been identified by both conjunctival biopsy and retinal capillaroscopy in patients with AH (Szulc et al. 2021). Microcirculation plays a key role in the regulation of the peripheral vascular resistance, which is a major determinant of AH. Clinical studies suggest that capillary rarefaction may be an early predictor and potential cause of the development of AH (Tomiyama and Shiina 2022).

Hypotheses about the relationship between microcirculation and hypertension

There are two main hypotheses. The first suggests that the increase in AH may be a consequence of functional and structural changes in microcirculation. This is initially thought to be a functional process, but as it persists, it becomes a structural abnormality (Rizzoni et al. 2023). The second hypothesis considers this peculiarity of microcirculation as a response to hypertension. Literature reports dilution in essential AH (Pries 2014; Triantafyllou et al. 2015; Triantafyllou et al. 2016), as well as dilution combined with dilatation of the venous section (Jordan and Shore 2017). Capillary density thinning has also been observed in patients without signs of increased AH, as well as in patients with high normal arterial pressure (HNAP) burdened with a family history of AH (Grassi et al. 2013; Triantafyllou et al. 2023). Dilution is also found in retinal vessels (Jianwen et al. 2019; Hanssen et al. 2022) of hypertensives, suggesting a systemic process.

Structural changes and remodeling of microcirculation in AH

A review of the importance of assessing microcirculation in the conjunctiva, retina, skin, and muscle capillaries is presented by Jung et al. (2013). One of the major microvascular changes characteristic of AH is structural remodeling, manifested by narrowing of arterial sections and dilation of the venous sections. This remodeling is assessed by calculating the ratio between the mean diameter of the arterial and venous segments.

Gurfinkel et al. (2014) proposed a remodeling coefficient that characterizes these vascular changes. Data on capillary remodeling are also observed in children born to mothers with AH, highlighting the possible long-term vascular effects of intrauterine hypertension (Antonios et al. 2012).

Microvascular rarefaction as a predictor for AH

Microvascular rarefaction, which is a common manifestation of AH, is closely associated with impaired angiogenesis, and early detection of microvascular rarefaction is essential for the systemic evaluation in hypertensive patients (Liang et al. 2019). In people with AH in the first or second stage, retinal capillary rarefaction has been found to increase with the duration of hypertension, compared with healthy controls with normal blood pressure (Bosch et al. 2017). Retinopathy and capillary thinning (in 40.9% of 66 hypertensives, Triantafyllou et al. 2014) are the most common target areas of damage among hypertensives. The number of affected organs is linearly correlated with the elevated Framingham scale score and serum aldosterone (Triantafyllou et al. 2014).

Capillaroscopy and non-invasive methods for the study of microcirculation

Capillaroscopy is relatively understudied and has only recently been applied as a non-invasive method of hypertension investigation (Triantafyllou et al. 2015). Microcirculation is subject to a series of morphological and functional changes under the continuous pressure of high AH. Of interest are also the microcirculatory changes that occur with sustained changes in hemodynamics in HNAP (Wright et al. 2006). In a study of young individuals with HNAP, microcirculatory changes were found when examining capillaries in the nail fold that were still functional (Bacelova et al. 2014). Non-invasive methods of HNAP examination identify early morphological and functional changes in macro- and microcirculation preceding the manifestation of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) and can be applied as an individual approach to assessment of CVR (Bacelova et al. 2019). Research recently has progressively focused on identifying specific microcirculatory changes that may serve as early prognostic markers of CVR. Dermal capillaries represent an “open window” for “in vivo” noninvasive and reliable study of human microcirculation (Rizzoni et al. 2018).

Opportunities for reverse microcirculatory changes in the treatment of arterial hypertension

Debbabi et al. described an increase in capillary density after treatment in patients with essential AH without diabetes (Debbabi et al. 2006). Treatment with a combined angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor (ACEI) and a diuretic affects the structural-functional parameters

of the heart and vessels. Perindopril/indapamide in full doses (10/2.5 mg) for 12 months improves the endothelial function, the structural and functional parameters of microcirculation, as well as the cognitive function in patients with arterial hypertension at high cardiovascular risk (Zheleznykh et al. 2016; Zheleznykh et al. 2018). Proper treatment, especially with the use of ACEIs, can improve microcirculation in patients with AH (Kowalik et al. 2022). Medications, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, and vascular angiotensin receptor blockers (AT1) induce angiogenesis “*in vivo*” in most animal studies. Furthermore, recent clinical studies have shown that long-term antihypertensive treatment increases capillary density in the skin of hypertensive patients without diabetes. These effects of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and AT1 receptor blockers may be mediated by activation of bradykinin pathways, leading to the generation of vascular endothelial growth factor, nitric oxide, and, consequently, angiogenesis (Battegay EJ 2007).

Correlations between microvascular and clinical-laboratory changes

A study by Mishra et al. (2021) supports the role of nail capillaroscopy for early detection of microvascular morphological changes in newly diagnosed patients with AH. These changes are more common and more distinct compared to healthy controls. The strong correlation found with the fundoscopic changes and microalbuminuria suggests that the method can be used for prediction and early diagnosis of cardiovascular and renal complications, and it has easy accessibility and good repeatability (Mishra et al. 2021).

A study analyzing the relationship between serum markers of inflammation (C-reactive protein (CRP), endothelin, adiponectin, I-CAM, and V-CAM) and microcirculatory parameters found that patients with severe hypertension and uncontrolled blood pressure levels who were not taking statins demonstrated more pronounced microvascular dysfunction and elevated serum CRP and endothelin levels. Evidence suggests that statin use may reduce the release of endothelin, which is one of the most potent vasoconstrictors (Junqueira et al. 2018).

In patients with AH, capillary density demonstrated a significant correlation with certain metabolic and demographic factors. There is a positive association between capillary density and high-density lipoproteins (HDL) ($r = 0.232$; $P = 0.003$), as well as with the HDL/LDL ratio ($r = 0.175$; $P = 0.025$). Furthermore, the results showed a statistically significant correlation between capillary density and the patients' age ($r = 0.236$; $P = 0.003$), suggesting that significant changes in the microcirculation occur with advancing age. Interestingly, no correlation was found between capillary density and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) or with the highly sensitive CRP, highlighting the complexity of the pathophysiological mechanisms regulating the microcirculatory function in hypertension.

Microvascular changes in metabolic disorders

Venous capillary segment dilation observed by capillaroscopy is associated with microcirculatory disorders in type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Decreased capillary density, increased capillary distortion, and capillary polymorphism are characteristic structural changes in T2DM. In decompensated diabetes mellitus, pronounced structural and functional abnormalities are found in the capillary bed, including narrowing of the arterial capillary segment, increased remodeling rate, and dilation of the venous capillary segment. Digital capillaroscopy opens new opportunities for objective assessment of microcirculatory changes in diabetes and can be a useful method for monitoring the effectiveness of the therapy (Suchkova et al. 2017).

There is evidence that microvascular dysfunction plays a key role not only in the pathogenesis of diabetes but also in the development of insulin resistance. A positive correlation has been found between perivascular capillary diapedesis observed in the nail fold of women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and HOMA-IR and serum testosterone levels (Koleva et al. 2017). In addition, abdominal obesity may play a significant role in increasing the percentage of cross capillaries in the nail fold in patients with T2DM (Shikama et al. 2021). These data support the need for combined assessment of capillaroscopic parameters, markers of insulin resistance, and body composition for more accurate determination of the metabolic risk.

Among the various metabolic mechanisms (diffusion, filtration-reabsorption, and vesicular), filtration-reabsorption metabolism is directly dependent on the hemodynamic parameters and plays an essential role in the exchange of water and low-molecular water-soluble substances (Fedorovich et al. 2018). Capillaroscopic studies have shown that administration of Actovegin results in significant changes in the hemodynamic parameters, including improved oxygen and glucose utilization, increased number of functioning capillaries, higher velocity of the capillary blood flow, and reduced interstitial hydration. These effects are associated with a decrease in capillary sphincter tone, which limits arteriolar-venous blood shunting, improves NO-mediated arteriolar regulation, and enhances the response to vasodilators. The results support the thesis that digital capillaroscopy is an informative method not only for assessing the functional state of microcirculation but also for analyzing the efficiency of filtration-reabsorption mechanisms of metabolism (Fedorovich et al. 2018).

There are suggestions that systemic metabolic disturbances at a capillary level are prevalent in men with newly diagnosed AH (Korolev et al. 2022). Clinical-functional studies of 118 men with newly diagnosed AH suggest that the major contribution to increased peripheral vascular resistance in the initial stages of hypertension is likely due to the large muscular arterioles, which are dominated by the neurogenic regulation of the vascular tone (Korolev et al. 2023).

Arterial stiffness, microcirculation, and metabolism

Arterial stiffness (AS) is a parameter reflecting the reduced ability of arteries to dilate and constrict in response to fluctuations in arterial pressure. AS is thought to be an indicator of the biological age of the vessels and is an independent predictor of cardiovascular diseases (Li et al. 2022).

Studies have shown that measured arterial stiffness does not correlate with cutaneous microvascular function regardless of the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) (van Sloten et al. 2015). The lack of association between AS and microcirculation highlights the need to expand diagnostic approaches for more accurate and comprehensive cardiovascular risk assessment.

Conclusion

Microcirculation plays a key role in the pathogenesis and progression of AH, and the structural and functional changes in the capillary network may serve as early markers of cardiovascular risk and other metabolic abnormalities. Digital capillaroscopy provides a reliable and non-invasive method of assessment of the microcirculatory changes occurring in the course of AH and can be a useful tool for diagnosis and monitoring of the disease.

Antihypertensive therapy, particularly with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACE inhibitors) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), can improve microcirculatory function and reduce vascular resistance, highlighting the importance of targeted therapy to optimize vascular homeostasis.

In the future, more in-depth studies on the interaction between microcirculation and the macrovascular system will contribute to the development of more precise strategies for prevention and therapy of arterial hypertension and its associated complications.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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